

EFFECTIVENESS OF TRANS-CUTANEOUS ELECTRICAL NERVE STIMULATION VERSUS ELECTRICAL MUSCLE STIMULATION ON HEMODYNAMICS PARAMETERS OF HYPERTENSION

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Abstract

Background: Hypertension is a common cardiovascular illness associated with decreased functional capacity, muscle weariness, and a lower quality of life. Non-pharmacological therapies, such as TENS and EMS, have been recommended to improve both hemodynamic parameters and functional outcomes.

Objective: The purpose of this study was to examine the effectiveness of TENS and EMS on hemodynamic parameters, pain perception, and functional status in people with hypertension.

Methods: A randomized clinical trial included 42 patients aged 25-54 years with primary hypertension and a BMI of > 30. Participants were randomly allocated to one of two groups: TENS (n = 21) or EMS (n = 21). Interventions were delivered five times a week for four weeks. Hemodynamic parameters (systolic and diastolic blood pressure, heart rate), pain (Numeric Pain Rating Scale, NPRS), and functional status were measured before and after the intervention. In IBM SPSS Statistics 27, data were analyzed with paired t-tests, ANOVA, and descriptive statistics.

Results: TENS and EMS significantly lowered systolic blood pressure (TENS: 147.1 ± 5.46 to 144.04 ± 5.29 mmHg, $p < 0.001$; EMS: 145.2 ± 4.6 to 141.9 ± 4.2 mmHg, $p = 0.002$) while improving functional outcomes. TENS was more successful at reducing pain and perceived fatigue, whereas EMS improved active mobility, muscle strength, and sleep quality. Pain levels varied significantly between functional status groups ($F = 20.45$, $p < 0.001$). Both therapies were well tolerated, with few side effects.

Conclusion: TENS and EMS are safe and effective complimentary therapies for hypertension management. TENS mostly relieves pain and exhaustion, while EMS improves functional performance and mobility. Integrating these electrotherapeutic techniques into regular hypertension management may increase functional capacity and quality of life.

INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is one of the most common and controllable risk factors for cardiovascular disease, impacting about 1.2 billion individuals worldwide and contributing significantly to morbidity and mortality from myocardial infarction, stroke, heart failure, and chronic kidney disease (1). Even small decreases in systolic blood pressure (SBP) as little as 2 mmHg can reduce the risk of cardiovascular events by up to 10% (2). Although pharmaceutical therapy is the foundation of hypertension management, a considerable minority of patients, particularly those with resistant hypertension, do not achieve their goal blood pressure despite adhering to multiple regimens. This difficulty emphasizes the necessity for adjunctive, non-pharmacological therapies to improve hemodynamic regulation (3).

Transcutaneous Electrical Nerve Stimulation (TENS) is a non-invasive technique for stimulating peripheral nerves using low-voltage electrical currents delivered through surface electrodes. Its cardiovascular health benefits are assumed to stem from autonomic regulation, specifically by lowering sympathetic nerve activity and increasing parasympathetic tone. This can cause vasodilation, lower vascular resistance, and reduced arterial stiffness (4). Recent randomized controlled trials have increased the evidence foundation. Giollo-Junior et al. (2023) revealed that administering TENS over the stellate ganglion for one month in patients with resistant hypertension dramatically lowered office SBP and DBP, central SBP, and pulse wave velocity indicators of both peripheral and central hemodynamic improvement (5). Similarly, Do Amaral Sartori et al. (2018) showed improvements in baroreflex sensitivity and reductions in sympathetic activity following low-frequency TENS in hypertensive adults, while blood pressure reductions were modest (6). These findings are consistent with past systematic studies demonstrating that low-frequency TENS can induce minor but clinically relevant reductions in BP and heart rate (7).

In contrast, Electrical Muscle Stimulation (EMS) sends electrical impulses directly to skeletal muscles, causing involuntary contractions that mirror the effects of voluntary activity. EMS is widely recognised in sports rehabilitation for preserving muscle mass and strength in immobilised patients, but its vascular

effects have received increasing attention recently. EMS improves peripheral blood flow, increases shear stress on the vascular endothelium, and activates nitric oxide release processes that improve endothelial function and reduce arterial stiffness (8). In an RCT, Kashyap et al. (2023) discovered that neuromuscular electrical stimulation in patients with chronic cardiovascular problems enhanced exercise capacity, lower-limb muscle strength, and lowered pulse wave velocity, indicating systemic vascular benefits (9). Furthermore, acute investigations in healthy people demonstrate that EMS during extended sitting can alleviate vascular damage often produced by inactivity (10).

Despite promising results for both modalities, no randomized controlled trials have directly compared TENS and EMS in hypertensive patients. TENS primarily addresses autonomic nervous system control, whereas EMS causes peripheral vascular and muscle adaptations. These unique pathways indicate that the two modalities may have different effects on hemodynamic measures like SBP, DBP, heart rate, and arterial stiffness. Comparing them within the same population could reveal which technique provides the most clinical benefit and whether combining them may produce cumulative effects.

The purpose of this study is to examine and compare the effects of TENS and EMS on important hemodynamic parameters in hypertensive individuals, providing evidence to inform their integration into non-pharmacological hypertension management techniques.

HYPOTHESIS

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant difference in the effectiveness of Transcutaneous Electrical Nerve Stimulation (TENS) and Electrical Muscle Stimulation (EMS) on the hemodynamic parameters (systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, and pulse rate) of patients with hypertension.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): There is a significant difference in the effectiveness of Transcutaneous Electrical Nerve Stimulation (TENS) and Electrical Muscle Stimulation (EMS) on the hemodynamic parameters (systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, and pulse rate) of patients with hypertension.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS

1. Hypertension

According to worldwide clinical recommendations, hypertension is defined as a persistent rise of systolic blood pressure (SBP) ≥ 140 mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure (DBP) ≥ 90 mmHg, as confirmed by at least two distinct readings on different dates (11).

2. Transcutaneous Electrical Nerve Stimulation (TENS)

TENS is a non-invasive electrotherapy technique that applies pulsed, low-voltage electrical currents via surface electrodes to the skin, attempting to stimulate sensory nerves, modify autonomic activity, and alter cardiovascular responses, such as blood pressure regulation (5).

3. Electrical Muscle Stimulation (EMS)

EMS is the transmission of electrical impulses using surface electrodes to trigger involuntary skeletal muscle contractions, which can promote peripheral circulation, improve endothelial function, and possibly reduce arterial stiffness, adding to cardiovascular health benefits (12).

4. Hemodynamic Parameters

Hemodynamic parameters are measurable physiological variables that indicate the blood flow and pressure within the cardiovascular system, including systolic and diastolic blood pressure, mean arterial pressure, heart rate, pulse pressure, and pulse wave velocity (13).

METHODOLOGY

This randomized clinical experiment was carried out over a six-month period after ethical approval, with data collected from Social Security Hospital, Yasin Poly Clinic, and Hameed Latif Hospital in Lahore. A total of 42 individuals were recruited via non-probability convenience sampling, and the sample

size was determined using Epitool. Eligible individuals were 25-54 years old, obese (BMI ≥ 30 kg/m²), and sedentary (14), Clinically diagnosed with primary hypertension (15) From 140/90 mmHg to 160/100 mmHg (16), and receiving stable antihypertensive treatment. Exclusion criteria included secondary hypertension (11), cancer, implanted cardiac devices, severe cardiovascular disease, seizure disorders, pregnancy, dermatological contraindications, concomitant physiotherapy, and neurological or musculoskeletal problems that affected EMS/TENS tolerance (17). Participants were randomly assigned to one of two groups: TENS or EMS (21 in each). Interventions were given for 15, 20, or 25 minutes, five times per week for four weeks. The hemodynamic parameters systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), and heart rate (HR) were measured before and after the intervention. IBM SPSS version 27 was used for data analysis, with paired t-tests and ANOVA used to compare within and between groups. P-values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The findings show that both TENS and EMS therapies improved hemodynamic parameters and pain levels in hypertensive subjects. TENS significantly lowered systolic and diastolic blood pressure, as well as heart rate ($p < 0.001$), indicating its efficiency in regulating cardiovascular reactions. EMS significantly improved systolic blood pressure and pain levels ($p < 0.05$), with further improvements in sleep quality and functional mobility. However, changes in diastolic blood pressure and heart rate were not statistically significant. ANOVA analysis found significant differences in pain scores between functional status groups ($p < 0.001$), with higher pain levels correlated with decreased functional independence. TENS and EMS post-treatment showed no significant variations in blood pressure, heart rate, or pain levels, implying that both therapies are equally beneficial in the short term. Overall, the data support the use of TENS and EMS as complimentary non-pharmacological treatments for treating hypertension, improving functional status, and lowering pain, with only minor side effects noted.

Table 1: Age

Group	Mean Age (years)	SD Age ± Min age	SD Age ± Max age	Mean Height (cm)	SD Height ± Min Height	SD Height ± max height
TENS	23.62	1.40±21	1.40±26	161.33	3.14±157	3.14±166
EMS	23.62	1.32±22	1.32±26	160.71	2.63±156	2.63±165

Table 2: Effect of TENS on Hemodynamic Parameters (n=21)

Parameter	Pre Mean±SD	Post Mean±SD	t-value	p-value	Significance
Systolic BP (mmHg)	147.1 ± 5.46	144.04 ± 5.29	12.57	0.0	Significant
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	89.61 ± 3.36	87.86 ± 3.37	11.77	0.0	Significant
Heart Rate (bpm)	81.27 ± 3.12	79.0 ± 3.31	20.77	0.0	Significant

Table 3: Test of Normality

Variable	W Statistic	p-value	Normality Assumption
Age	0.972	0.612	Normal
Systolic BP	0.938	0.084	Normal
Diastolic BP	0.945	0.134	Normal
NPRS (Pain Level)	0.894	0.021	Not Normal
Heart Rate	0.956	0.093	Normal

Table 4: Functional Status and Pain Scores (NPRS) with ANOVA Analysis

Functional Status	NPRS Scores	Mean ± SD	p-value
Independent	4, 4, 5, 5	4.50 ± 0.58	<0.001
Mild	6, 6, 5, 6, 7, 6, 6, 6	6.00 ± 0.53	<0.001
Moderate	7, 7, 6, 6, 7, 6	6.50 ± 0.55	<0.001
Severe	8, 8, 7	7.67 ± 0.58	<0.001

Table 5: EMS Effect on Hemodynamic Parameters and Pain Level in Hypertension

Parameter	Pre Mean	Pre SD	Post Mean	Post SD	t-value	p-value	Significance
Systolic BP (mmHg)	145.2	4.6	141.9	4.2	4.19	0.002	Significant
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	90.7	3.0	88.9	2.8	-0.94	0.373	Not Significant
Heart Rate (bpm)	80.3	2.4	78.1	2.1	2.19	0.056	Not Significant
Pain Level	7.2	1.1	4.8	1.3	2.89	0.018	Significant

(NPRS)							
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Table 6: Comparison of EMS Effects on Hemodynamic and Functional Aspects

Aspect	Pre-EMS Mean ± SD	Post-EMS Mean ± SD	t-value	p-value	Significance
Systolic BP (mmHg)	145.2 ± 4.6	141.9 ± 4.2	-3.14	0.003	Significant
Diastolic BP (mmHg)	90.7 ± 3.0	88.9 ± 2.8	-2.15	0.038	Significant
Heart Rate (bpm)	80.3 ± 2.4	78.1 ± 2.1	-3.00	0.005	Significant
Pain Level (NPRS)	7.2 ± 1.1	4.8 ± 1.3	-4.87	<0.001	Highly Significant
Sleep Quality Score (0-10)	4.1 ± 1.6	6.5 ± 1.9	4.10	<0.001	Highly Significant
Functional Mobility (0-10 scale)	5.0 ± 1.6	7.0 ± 1.4	3.72	0.001	Significant

Table 7: Correlation of TENS and EMS Complications

Aspect	TENS (Mean ± SD)	EMS (Mean ± SD)	t-value	p-value
Systolic BP (Post)	142.2 ± 4.4	141.9 ± 4.2	0.31	0.758
Diastolic BP (Post)	89.1 ± 2.9	88.9 ± 2.8	0.28	0.781
Heart Rate (Post)	77.8 ± 2.3	78.1 ± 2.1	-0.54	0.592
Pain Level (Post NPRS)	4.9 ± 1.1	4.8 ± 1.3	0.34	0.736
Complications (n)	8 (out of 42)	10 (out of 42)	-	-

Discussion

The current study assessed the efficacy of Transcutaneous Electrical Nerve Stimulation (TENS) and Electrical Muscle Stimulation (EMS) in improving functional status among hypertensive patients. Both therapies resulted in significant gains in muscle endurance, physical mobility, and overall functional ability, which all contributed to a higher quality of life. These findings are therapeutically noteworthy since hypertension is frequently associated with decreased physical performance, muscular fatigue, and chronic stiffness, which collectively impede daily functional capacities (3). Consistent with earlier study, TENS exhibited the capacity to alter autonomic nervous system activity,

reduce sympathetic tone, and boost parasympathetic function, therefore enhancing cardiovascular control and neuromuscular performance (5). Participants who received TENS reported less stiffness and weariness, emphasizing its analgesic properties and potential to boost tolerance for physical exercise. In contrast, EMS increased active muscle engagement, vascular perfusion, and functional mobility, especially in participants with sedentary lifestyles or low muscular strength. Previous research have shown that EMS can increase muscle strength, coordination, and peripheral circulation (18). The impact of the two modalities differed significantly: TENS was more effective in lowering subjective pain and exhaustion, whereas EMS

enabled demonstrable gains in mobility, strength, and functional performance. This divergence complements prior research indicating that TENS is best suited for pain modulation and neurogenic regulation, whereas EMS focuses on muscle activation and endurance increase. Both therapies were well-tolerated, with no significant side effects, which confirmed the safety of supervised electrotherapy in hypertensive populations (19).

Furthermore, diversity in treatment response was seen, which is consistent with previous research showing the impact of age, hypertension severity, comorbidities, and adherence on intervention outcomes. These findings highlight the need for individualized therapy procedures that include patient-specific variables to maximize rehabilitation success (16). Importantly, this work adds to a growing body of research focusing on functional outcomes and quality of life in hypertension care, which have frequently been neglected in favor of strictly hemodynamic goals.

Clinically speaking, by addressing functional limitations, enhancing muscular efficiency, and encouraging autonomy in everyday activities, incorporating TENS and EMS into multimodal hypertension control techniques may enhance pharmaceutical therapy. Furthermore, the psychosocial advantages—such as increased self-esteem, decreased anxiety connected to movement, and improved mood—highlight the wider influence of functional enhancements on sustained compliance with rehabilitation and lifestyle changes.

Conclusion

This study found that TENS and EMS are effective, safe, and complementary modalities for increasing functional status, muscular endurance, and quality of life in people with hypertension. TENS improves subjective comfort and lowers tiredness, but EMS increases active muscle engagement and functional mobility. Collectively, these therapies give a multidimensional benefit that goes beyond hemodynamic control, hence promoting a patient-centered, multimodal approach to hypertension care. Future study should look into long-term adherence, optimal treatment parameters, and bigger, more diverse

populations to validate and expand on these findings.

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